

EARTH SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF NEW THERMAL REGULATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR ENERGY-EFFICIENT CONSTRUCTION IN REGIONS WITH EXTREME CLIMATE CONDITIONS

Yarov Y.

Kyrgyz National University named after Zhusup Balasagyn

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes modern thermal regulation technologies for energy-efficient construction and examines the effectiveness of these systems under extreme climate change conditions. The study explores innovative insulating materials, such as aerogels, vacuum insulation panels, and phase-change materials (PCM), as well as smart facades, which help reduce heat transfer and enhance energy efficiency. The use of RES, including solar, geothermal, and wind systems, is also considered for maintaining optimal temperature control.

Keywords: thermal regulation, energy efficiency, aerogels, phase-change materials (PMC), smart facades, renewable energy, solar power, geothermal systems.

Introduction

In developed countries, enhancing energy efficiency is becoming a crucial consideration in the planning and building of structures, particularly in areas with severe weather conditions. There is a demand for advanced thermal management technologies to ensure comfortable indoor conditions with low energy usage in challenging climates like extreme winters, hot summers, high winds, and quick temperature changes. Conventional methods for managing temperature frequently fail to maintain a consistent indoor climate and typically result in high energy expenses.

In this regard, there is a growing need to improve both active and passive thermal control methods, as well as the integration of renewable energy sources (RES). New materials used in modern heat pumps can greatly enhance the energy efficiency of buildings. This is particularly crucial in regions with harsh climates, where expenses for heating and cooling can be notable.

Moreover, assessing the economic and environmental advantages of these technologies is crucial. Incorporating sources of renewable energy like solar and

geothermal power into thermal systems helps lessen reliance on non-renewable sources and aids in cutting down greenhouse gas emissions. This emphasizes the significance of using such technologies to develop energy-efficient buildings that are sustainable and can withstand extreme weather conditions. The goal of this research is to examine and assess contemporary thermal control technologies that can greatly enhance energy efficiency in the building sector.

Main part. Overview of thermal regulation technologies

Over the past few decades, the Earth's average temperature has steadily increased due to the effects of climate change. This rise in global temperatures has led to more frequent and intense heatwaves, causing severe disruptions in both natural and human systems. In 2023, the global land surface temperature was 1,81°C above the global average between 1901 and 2000, according to the 2024 statistics [1]. This represents the highest annual temperature anomaly recorded during the period under consideration (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Annual anomalies in global land surface temperature from 1980 to 2023, based on temperature departure, °C

As global temperatures continue to climb, the demand for energy has risen significantly, especially in sectors related to heating and cooling. Buildings, in par-

particular, are consuming more energy to maintain comfortable indoor environments during extreme weather conditions. In 2023, global energy consumption exhibited accelerated growth (+2.2%) [2].

Various thermal regulation technologies have been developed to tackle the challenges of extreme climate conditions due to the growing need for energy efficiency and climate resilience. These advancements include new materials and advanced systems that aim to enhance indoor temperatures, decrease energy use, and enhance the overall sustainability of buildings [3].

Modern insulation materials are crucial in reducing heat transfer from the inside to the outside of a building. Famous for their extremely low thermal conductivity, **aerogels** are lightweight, highly porous substances that provide excellent insulation capabilities. Their nano-structure allows them to offer outstanding heat resistance while still being very thin.

Aerogels are particularly valuable in preventing heat loss during cold winters and reducing heat gain during hot summers. An example of a modern aerogel is the hypocrySTALLINE zircon nanofibrous aerogel with a zig-zag structure, which is designed to improve thermal insulation performance. It achieves a remarkably low high-temperature thermal conductivity of 104 mW/m·K at 1,000°C [4].

Similar to aerogels, **insulation materials** enhanced with nanotechnology provide a significant improvement in energy efficiency. These materials can include coatings, films, or panels that offer superior thermal insulation by using nanoparticles to create barriers that limit heat transfer.

Vacuum Insulation Panels (VIP) are among the effective materials. They are made up of a central substance contained within a vacuum-sealed casing. The panel's high insulation efficiency comes from the vacuum's ability to significantly reduce heat transfer through conduction and convection. Being slender and light, they are perfect for situations with limited space, like updating old buildings or insulating thin walls.

Phase-Change Materials (PCM) offer a cutting-edge and efficient method to control indoor temperatures through their capacity to store and release significant thermal energy when undergoing phase shifts. All PCM function by taking in heat as they transition from a solid to a liquid form and giving off that heat as they change back from a liquid to a solid state [5]. This unique property allows them to act as thermal buffers, stabilizing indoor temperatures by mitigating sudden spikes or drops in heat. Solid-solid PCM are most commonly used in window applications, where PCM-filled glazed windows can reduce peak indoor temperatures by up to 9°C. Additionally, when integrated into roofs, PCM have been shown to lower peak temperatures by 1°C-7°C and reduce heat loads by 19%-59%, providing substantial energy savings and enhanced thermal comfort [6].

In this regard, windows are often one of the weakest points in a building's thermal envelope. However, advancements in glazing technology have significantly improved the thermal performance of windows, reducing both heat loss in winter and heat gain in summer. Key innovations in this area include:

- **Double and triple glazing:** these systems consist of multiple layers of glass with gaps between them that are filled with insulating gases like argon or krypton. This intricate design significantly reduces heat transfer, and the thermal performance of the glass can be enhanced by applying coatings that reflect infrared radiation and allow natural light to enter.

- **Low-E coatings** are thin metallic layers that are placed on the surface of glass to send heat back into the building in winter and reflect solar heat away in summer. This assists in keeping the indoor temperature stable, which decreases the reliance on extra heating or cooling.

Smart facades, also known as intelligent building exteriors, make use of adaptive technologies to respond dynamically to the surroundings, representing a notable progress in design. By adjusting their properties based on outside temperature, sunlight, and wind, these systems regulate the heat exchange within the building.

Dynamic glazing is a smart facade that utilizes electrochromic glass, capable of adjusting its transparency based on external factors. The glass darkens to decrease heat gain when exposed to sunlight, and becomes clearer in colder weather to let in more sunlight and warmth. The thermal properties of **thermally adaptive panels** can adjust according to the conditions in the surrounding environment. In warm climates, panels bounce off sunlight and lower heat intake, whereas in cold climates, they soak up more heat to sustain a cozy interior temperature.

These advanced materials and systems provide a complete solution for thermal regulation in buildings. Through the use of both active and passive technologies, construction projects in extreme climate areas can save a lot of energy, enhance indoor comfort, and lessen their environmental footprint.

Utilization of RES for thermal regulation

Incorporating RES like solar and geothermal energy into thermal regulation systems has multiple benefits, including reducing dependence on fossil fuels, cutting energy expenses, and promoting environmental sustainability. These technologies could be established as a standard within environmental regulations and guidelines [7]. Solar energy is frequently utilized as a renewable option for regulating temperature.

Solar panels, also known as photovoltaic systems, transform sunlight into power for heating and cooling systems. Solar panels are effective in sunny areas, fulfilling a large part of a building's energy requirements and diminishing dependence on traditional energy sources. Furthermore, solar panels can also support running active thermal regulation systems like heating, ventilation, and air conditioning units, thus enhancing energy efficiency. Various kinds of solar panels show much better performance nowadays than in the early days of solar technology development (table 1).

Table 1.

Comparison of efficiency with different generations of cells [8]

Generation	Type of solar cell	Module efficiency (%)	Applications
First generation	Monocrystalline type	14-17,5	Used in conventional surroundings
	Polycrystalline type	12-14	
Second generation	Thin film solar cells	16-17	Used in BiPV on smaller power systems
	Copper Indium Gallium Selenide (CIGS)	10-12	
Third generation	Amorphous silicon	4-8	Best suited for areas with normal irradiation
	Nanocrystal	7-8	
	Dye-sensitized	10	
	Polymer	3-10	
	Perovskites	31	
	Cadmium Tellurium (CdTe) type solar cell	9-11	

Scientists observe that the majority of crystalline solar cells are capable of absorbing 90% of irradiance within the range of 400 to 1200 nm. However, the conversion efficiency is limited to a maximum of 18%, with the remaining energy being converted into heat.

Solar thermal collectors collect and store solar energy for the purpose of heating. Solar thermal collectors are frequently utilized to warm water or air, which can be circulated within the building to keep a consistent indoor temperature. These systems work best in sunny regions, but can also be paired with other energy sources for a hybrid system that provides climate control year-round.

Passive solar heating involves designing buildings to optimize solar energy without needing mechanical systems. Passive solar heating enables a building to gather, retain, and circulate solar energy naturally by utilizing large windows, careful positioning, and heat-absorbing materials. This technique decreases the necessity for extra heating and is a crucial element of eco-friendly design in areas with significant sunlight.

Geothermal energy is a very efficient renewable source that is utilized for controlling indoor temperatures, especially in areas with harsh climates. **Geothermal heat pumps**, also called ground-source heat pumps, move heat from a building to the ground. During winter, geothermal heat pumps extract warmth from the Earth to heat the building, and in summer, the heat is transferred back into the ground to cool the building. Geothermal heat pumps are highly efficient because they utilize the constant temperature beneath the Earth's surface, which is not impacted by extreme surface weather conditions [9].

Through integrating solar and geothermal energy in thermal regulation systems, buildings can attain a strong level of energy self-sufficiency, greatly diminish their carbon emissions, and improve their ability to withstand extreme weather events. The ongoing development of these sustainable energy technologies provides a viable way forward for the construction sector.

Conclusion

Using advanced heat management technologies such as solar, geothermal, wind, and passive systems is vital in addressing the growing challenges of climate change and severe weather conditions. Decreasing dependence on traditional energy sources improves building sustainability and efficiency through sustainable energy alternatives. Advanced materials, intelligent

technologies, and integrated methods in construction can result in sustainable buildings that fulfill both present and future energy requirements. The progress of urban areas can be significantly influenced by the development of these technologies.

References

1. Annual anomalies in global land surface temperature from 1880 to 2023, based on temperature departure / Statista // URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1048518/average-land-sea-temperature-anomaly-since-1850/> (date of application: 10.10.2024).
2. Total energy consumption / Enerdata // URL: <https://yearbook.enerdata.net/total-energy/world-consumption-statistics.html> (date of application: 12.10.2024).
3. Stepanov M. Strategies for enhancing reliability and reducing energy consumption of electrical equipment in industry // Proceedings of the XLIII International Multidisciplinary Conference «Prospects and Key Tendencies of Science in Contemporary World». Bubok Publishing S.L., Madrid, Spain. 2024.
4. Guo J., Fu S., Deng Y., Xu X., Laima S., Liu D., Zhang P., Zhou J., Zhao H., Yu H., Dang S. Hypocrystalline ceramic aerogels for thermal insulation at extreme conditions // Nature. 2022. Vol. 606. No. 7916. P. 909-916.
5. Konstantinov D., Kolganov D. Adaptation refrigeration systems to extreme temperature conditions due to climate change: challenges and solutions // Cold Science. 2024. No. 6. P. 31-39.
6. Reddy V.J., Ghazali M.F., Kumarasamy S. Advancements in phase change materials for energy-efficient building construction: A comprehensive review // Journal of Energy Storage. 2024. Vol. 81. P. 110494.
7. Uliankina I. Integration of environmental standards into American companies: analysis of methods and practical solutions // International independent scientific journal. 2024. No. 65. P. 8-11.
8. Parthiban R., Ponnambalam P. An enhancement of the solar panel efficiency: a comprehensive review // Frontiers in Energy Research. 2022. Vol. 10. P. 937155.
9. Wang P., Wang Y., Gao W., Xu T., Wei X., Shi C., Qi Z., Bai L. Uncovering the Efficiency and Performance of Ground-Source Heat Pumps in Cold Regions: A Case Study of a Public Building in Northern China // Buildings. 2023. Vol. 13. No. 6. P. 1564.